

Inaccuracies of Contra distinguishing Adjectives and Adverbs that Perpetrated via EFL Students at ME in Kurdistan Region, Iraq

by

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Abstract

The paper shows the inaccuracies of contradistinguishing adjectives and adverbs perpetrated by EFL students at the Ministry of Education in the Kurdistan region, Iraq. The paper investigates about two main theories. The first one is that students of EFL at ME are not mindful of differentiating adjectives and adverbs. The second theory is that students at ME cannot extrapolate adjectives from an adverb. To confirm or reject the theories of the study, the researcher used a test designed for the students of higher school as a research tool. The sample of this study was randomly selected, twenty students. The numerical data collected from these subjects were statistically analyzed and the results were discussed. The results of the study confirm that students of EFL at ME can't derive an adjective from an adverb and the opposite. Whereas the result of the study shows that the students of EFL at ME are aware of adjectives and adverbs, and they use adjectives and adverbs correctly from a morphological point. Finally, the researcher could find the problems of the students that why they cannot use and recognize adjectives and adverbs, and this is the real problem in the process of language acquisition at the level of higher school. So the paper has conclusions and recommendations that will be agate for students at higher school in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq.

Keywords: Inaccuracies, contradistinguishing, adjectives, adverbs, Kurdistan region, perpetrated, etc.

Introduction:

Most students of EFL at the level of higher school and university in the Kurdistan Region have errors in applying the rules of syntactic structure (Hazhar, 2020a&b). They are unable to differentiate between parts of speech from morphological and syntactical points of view. English words have been traditionally classified into eight parts of speech which are noun, pronoun, adjective, verb, adverb, preposition, conjunction, and interjection. The focus in this research is on two of them i.e. adjective and adverb from morphological and syntactical points. Sometimes students of English language fail in differentiating between adjective and adverb and this creates a big problem for them to understand English sentences.

Definition of Adjectives:

According to Longan (2004), adjectives describe the “name of a person, place or things or pronouns.” Another definition of adjectives is that “an adjective is a word that describes a

noun or pronoun. Adjectives may limit or change the meaning of a noun” (Walker, 1982). Brandon (2011) notes that adjectives modify nouns and pronouns. Most adjectives answer the questions “what kind? which one? and how many?” Adjectives answering “what kind?” questions are descriptive and tell the quality, kind, or condition of the nouns or pronouns they modify, for example dirty fork, wild roses, and red convertible. Adjectives answering “which one?” question narrow or restrict the meaning of a noun. Some of these are pronouns that become adjectives by function e.g. my money, our ideas. Adjectives answering “how many?” question is, of course, and number words, e. g. Three dollars, one glove, some people, each pet, a few goals.

Thomson (1986) writes that “adjectives in English have the same form for singular and plural, masculine and feminine nouns,” for example, “a good boy, good boys, a good girl, good girls.” The only exceptions are the demonstrative adjectives “this and that,” which change to “these and those” before plural nouns, e.g. “This cat, these cats” and “that man, those men.”

Kinds of Adjectives:

Thomson et al, (1986) has mentioned the following main kinds of adjectives:

- i. **Demonstrative:** This, that, these, those.
- ii. **Distributive:** each, every, either, and neither.
- iii. **Quantitative:** some, any, no, little, few, many, much.
- iv. **Interrogative:** which, what, whose.
- v. **Possessive:** my, yours, his, her, its, our, their.
- vi. **Of quality:** clever, dry, fat, golden, good, heavy, and square.

Descriptive adjective or adjective quality:

Descriptive adjectives are the most numerous of the different types of adjectives. These adjectives describe nouns that refer to an action, state, or quality careless, dangerous, excited, sad, black, white, big, and fat, e. g. dangerous chemicals, green vegetables, a big house, etc.

Adjective of quality:

An adjective of quality tells us the number “how many” or amount “how much” of a noun, e. g. “He has eaten three apples.” “I do not have much money.” “ There is so much wine for the guests.”

Demonstrative adjective:

A demonstrative adjective modifies nouns in singular or plural form or points out a fact about the noun e. g. “This cute baby is his brother.” “That cute baby is his sister.” “These two fat cats have tails.” “That thin cat does not have a tail.”

Possessive adjective:

A possessive adjective expresses possession of a noun by someone as possessive pronouns. All the possessive adjectives are listed in the following table:

Table 1: Possessive Adjectives

Singular	Plural
We	Our
Your	Your
His	Their
Her	Their
Its	Their

Examples of possessive adjectives are as follows:

- i. I spent my afternoon cleaning the toilet.
- ii. This must be your cap.
- iii. His arms have a few tattoos.
- iv. Its skin is dry and rough.
- v. Our grandmothers were classmates.

Function of Adjective:

Swan (1998:9) writes that most adjectives can go in two main places in a sentence before a noun “attributive position,” such as:

- i. The secretary does not like me.
- ii. He is going out with a rich businesswoman.

And after be, seem, look, become, and other verbs.

- iii. That dress is new. Is it?
- iv. She looks rich.
- v. I feel happy.

Adjectives used as attributive are used only or mostly in attributive position. After a verb, other words must be used. Common examples of such adjectives are elder and eldest mainly in British English comparison, e. g.

- i. My elder sister is a pilot; she is three years older than me.
- ii. A live fish; It’s still alive.

When several adjectives come before a noun or when nouns are used to modify another noun, they usually have to be put in a particular order. For instance, saying “a fat old lady,” is right while “an old fat lady” is not. Unfortunately, the rules for adjective order are very complicated and different grammars disagree about the details. Here are some of the most important rules:

- i. Color, origin, material and purpose adjectives, modifying nouns of color, origin, material and purpose usually go in the following order (Table 2):

Table 2: Several Adjectives

Color	Origin	Material	Purpose	Nouns	Phrases
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Red	Spanish	Leather	Riding	Boots	Red Spanish leather riding boots
Brown	German		Bear	Mug	Brown German bear mug
	Venetian	Glass	Flower	Vase	Venetian glass flower vase

- ii. Other adjectives: other adjectives usually go before words of color, origin, material and purpose, it is impossible to give exact rules, but adjectives of size, length and height often came first, e.g. “The round glass table” not “the glass round table.”
- iii. Judgment and attitudes: Adjectives which express judgment or attitudes usually came before all others e.g. “lovely, definite, pure, absolute, extreme, perfect, wonderful, silly, long, cool drink, who’s that silly fat man over there?” etc.
- iv. Numbers: Numbers usually go before adjectives, e.g. “six large eggs,” “the second big shock.” First next and last most often go before one two three, etc. e.g. “the first three days” or “ my last two jobs.”

Law (1984) claim and classify adjectives by position. This means that syntactically, adjectives modify nouns in the following three positions:

- a. Adherent: immediately preceding the noun i.e. The brave soldier has come.
- b. Predicate: standing in the predicate position, i. e. in “subject complement,” “The film is interesting” and as “Objective complement, “The teacher considers the solution wrong.”
- c. Appositive: standing beside its substantive in a relation similar to a noun in a position. For example, “Her baby angry and nervous refused to have his meal.”

Thomson (1986: 33) notes that adjectives have attributive and predicative use.

Comparative and Superlative adjectives:

Lagon (2004: 219) notes, for using adjectives to compare we use –er when comparing two things. For example, “ I am taller than my brother, but my father is the tallest person in the house.” We use more when comparing three or more things.

According to Swan (1998: 119), a one-syllable adjective normally has a comparative and superlative ending in –er, -est. some two-syllable adjectives have more and most (Table 3).

Table 3: One syllable adjective “regular comparison”

Adjective	Comparative	Superlative
long	longer	longest
hot	hotter	hottest
late	later	latest
big	bigger	biggest
fat	fatter	fattest

Adjectives ending –y have –er and est, especially adjectives ending in an unstressed vowel /i/ or /au (Table 4).

Table 4: Two syllable adjectives

Adjective	Comparative	Superlative
narrow	narrower	narrowest
simple	simpler	simplest

Longer adjectives:

Adjectives of three or more syllables have more and most, e.g.

- i. Intelligent, more intelligent, most intelligent
- ii. Practical, more practical, most practical

Words like unhappy “the opposite of two-syllable adjective ending in – y” are an exception. For example,

- i. Unhappy, unhappier, unhappiest
- ii. Untidy, untidier, untidiest

Irregular forms:

Langon (2004: 219) notes pay more attention to the following words, each of which has irregular forms:

Table 5: Irregular forms of adjectives

Adjectives	Comparative	Superlative
bad	worse	worst
good , well	better	best
little	less	least
much, many	more	most

Adjective suffixes:

Suffixes word ending come at the end of a word. They show whether the word is a verb, noun, adjective, or adverb. These are common word ending for the adjective, with their meanings and examples in the table 6.

Table 6: adjective suffixes

Suffixes endings	Meanings	Examples
-es	From a place	Japanese, Chinese
-ical	“to make adjective from nouns ending in-y or ics” connected with	economical, physical and mathematical
-ing	Producing a particular state or effect	Interesting
-ish	describing nationality or language, like something, fairly, sort of	English, Swedish Polish and foolish
-like	Similar to	Dislike
-y	Having the quality of the thing mentioned	Cloudy and rainy
-ive	doing or tending to ward doing some action	extensive, selective
-en	made of: note: when the word is an adjective he –en means made of. We have seen –en at the end of the verb. There it means to make.	wooden
-ice	means characteristics of: like	heroic, poetic
-able	means able, can or giving	portable
-al	Sometimes makes a adjective it means relation to	Financial, manual
-y	means having	hairy, rainy
-ous	means full of having	mysterious
-full	Means full of: having	hopeful
-less	means without	powerless, homeless

Definition of Adverbs:

A word belonging to one of the major form classes in any of numerous language, typically serving as a modifier of a verb, an adjective, another adverb, a preposition, a phrase, a clause, or a sentence, expressing some relation of manner, cause, opposition, affirmation, or denial and in English also serving to connect and to express comment on clause content.

Adverbs as words that are used to give more information about verbs. They can be used to describe the action, give more information about when, where, and how of the action, or to compare actions. Adverbs can also be used to give more information about adjectives “word that describes a noun-a person, place or thing” or joins two phrases together. Adverbs that join together two phrases are called conjunctive adverbs.

Kinds of Adverbs:

The main categories of adverbs:

- i. Adverb of Time: yesterday, today, tonight, tomorrow, now, nowadays, presently, then, suddenly. “ She will come tomorrow.” “Suddenly, I heard a noise.”
- ii. Adverb of Frequency: never, ever, occasionally, sometimes, often, usually, generally, always. “ I often think about him” and “ She is always late.
- iii. Adverb of Manner: slowly, quickly, kindly, nicely, sadly, happily, quietly. “He sleeps quietly,” and “I asked nicely.”
- iv. Adverb of Place: here, there, inside, outside, everywhere. “Come here.” “I will be there.”
- v. Adverb of Quantity/Degree: very, enough, so, too, extremely. “We were very satisfied.” “It is extremely interesting.”

- vi. Adverb of Connection: however, therefore, consequently, anyway, nevertheless, accordingly. “However, the second one was not as popular.” “Anyway, let’s do it.”
- vii. Adverb of Probability/opinion: maybe, perhaps, possibly, surely, certainly, honestly, personally. “This could possibly happen.” “Personally, I would not buy this product.”

Function of Adverbs:

The English word adverb derives “through French” from Latin adverbium, from ad. “To”, verb um “word verb” and the nominal suffix –ium. The term implies that the principal function of adverb is to act as modifiers of a verb or verb phrase. An adverb used in this way may provide information about the manner, place, time, frequency, certainty or other circumstances of the activity denoted by the verb or verb phrase. Examples of adverbs are:

- i. She sang loudly “loudly modifies the verb sang, indicating the manner of singing”.
- ii. We left it here “here modifies the verb phrase left it, indicating place”.
- iii. I worked yesterday “yesterday modifies the verb work, indicating time”.
- iv. You often make mistakes “often modifies the verb phrase to make mistakes, indicating frequency”.
- v. He undoubtedly did it “undoubtedly modifies the verb phrase did it, indicating certainty”.

Adverbs can also be used as modifiers of adjectives and of other adverbs, often to indicate a degree. e.g.

- i. You are quite right “the adverb quite modifies the adjective right”.
- ii. She sang very loudly “the adverb very modifies another adverb “loudly”.

They can also modify determiners, prepositional phrases or whole clauses or sentences, like the following:

- i. I bought practically the only fruit “practically modifies the determiner “the” in the noun phrase” the only fruit” wherein “only” is an adjective”.
- ii. Certainly, we need to act “certainly modifies the sentence as a whole”.
- iii. She drove us almost to the station “almost modifies the prepositional phrase “to the station”.

Adverbs thus perform a wide range of modifying functions. The most major exception is the function of the modifier of the noun, which is performed instead by adjectives “compare she sang loudly with her loud singing disturbed, me, here the verb sang is modified by the adverb loudly, whereas the noun singing is modified by the adjective loud”. However, because some adverbs and adjectives are homonyms, their respective functions are sometimes conflicted.

- i. Even numbers are divisible by two.
- ii. The camel even drank.

The word “even” in the first sentence is an adjective since it is a prepositive modifier that modifies the noun “number.” The second sentence is a prepositive adverb that modifies the verb “drank.” Although it is possible for an adverb to precede or to follow a noun or a noun phrase, the adverb nonetheless does not modify either in such cases as in:

- i. Internationally there is a shortage of protein for animal feeds.
- ii. There is an internationally shortage of protein for animal feeds.

In the first sentence “internationally” is a prepositive adverb that modifies the clause, “there is” by contrast, the third sentence contains “internationally” as a prepositive adjective that modifies the noun “shortage”.

Adverbs can sometimes be used as predicative expressions in English, this applies especially to adverbs of location e.g. “Your seat is there.” When the function of an adverb is performed by an expression consisting of more than one word, it is called an adverbial phrase or adverbial clause, or simply, an adverbial.

Significance of the Study:

This study is important because it is going to shed the light on the students’ inaccuracies in the use of adjectives and adverbs. The study will also investigate to what extent they are able to contradistinguish between them.

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- i. The errors faced by the students at the higher school level in recognizing the adjectives and adverbs in usage.
- ii. Measuring the students’ knowledge about adjectives and adverbs from the morphological point.
- iii. Recognizing the higher school students’ foreign language ability to differentiate between adjectives and adverbs from the morphological view.

Statement of the problem:

The problem is that a lot of students of EFL at ME confused between the use of Adjectives and Adverbs, from syndetic and morphological points.

Questions of the study:

This paper addresses the following questions:

- i. To what degree are the students of EFL at ME aware of adjectives and adverbs?
- ii. To what extent the students of EFL at ME use adjectives and adverbs morphologically correct?
- iii. To what degree can the students of EFL at ME drive adjectives from adverbs and the opposite?
- iv. Is there any significant difference between the students of higher school in their ability to differentiate between adjective and adverb?

Hypotheses of the study:

The study will test the following hypotheses:

- i. Students of EFL at ME are not aware of adjectives and adverbs.
- ii. Students of EFL at ME cannot derive adjectives from adverbs and vice versa.

The sample of the Study:

The sample of this study is chosen randomly, and it is about twenty (20) students from higher school. So the sample of this study, students of the higher school at the Ministry of Education in Kurdistan Region, Iraq.

The Population of the Study:

The populations of this study are Kurdish students of higher school, aged 17 to 21 with Kurdish as their mother language.

Data Collection:

Data of this study have been collected by using a test which consists of two questions and each question has ten items.

Statistical Measurement:

After the data collected it would be analyzed by SPSS “statistical package and social studies.”

Data Analysis, Results and Discussions

Hypothesis One - Students of EFL at ME are not aware of aware and adverbs:

Table 7: Hypothesis one

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid correct	169	60.2	60.2	60.2
incorrect	72	39.8	39.8	39.8
Total	250	100.0	100.0	

From the table above 60.2% was the correct answer to question one to students of EFL at ME first year. According to these result the first hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis Two - Students of EFL at ME cannot derive an adjective from an adverb and the opposite:

Table 8: Hypothesis two

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Valid correct	65	20.1	20.1	20.1
incorrect	185	79.9	79.9	79.9
Total	250	100.0	100	

20.1% was the correct answer to question two, to the students of first year. According to this result, the second hypothesis is accepted.

The results:

The study was operated by the researcher through the sample of the examination, conducted by the group of students at ME, of which the vast majority did not achieve a lower percent in the first question, so the first hypothesis was rejected, which means they are aware of the use of adjectives and adverbs. But the second hypothesis was accepted because the students did not achieve the required percentage for success, which means they should try to practice and drive the adjective from the adverb and vice versa.

Conclusion:

On the basis of the results, following are concluded:

- i. Students of higher school as foreign language students face difficulties in deriving the adjectives from the adverb and vice-versa.
- ii. Students of higher school as foreign language students at the ME do mistakes when they use suffixes to drive an adjective from an adverb and vice versa.
- iii. Students of EFL at ME are aware of adjectives and adverbs.
- iv. Students of EFL at ME cannot derive an adjective from an adverb and vice-versa.

Recommendations:

On the basis of the conclusion, following are recommended:

- i. Teachers have to give more academic practical details at ME about Adjectives and Adverbs.
- ii. Higher School students at ME should do more practices for differentiating between adjectives and adverbs.
- iii. Researchers of English Language teaching have to do more papers about the ways of contradistinguishing adjectives from adverbs.

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